

Empowering Student Voice: English Day Programs and The Development Of Speaking Self Confidence Among EFL Learners

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ABSTRACT: Each student possesses different abilities, knowledge as well as speaking competence, and it was influenced by many factors including their self confidence. This study aims to know the development of students' speaking self-confidence especially for English Department students at Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku. The samples are 20 students who had been participated in English day program, and it taken randomly. The instruments consist of observation, questionnaire and interview. This study used a descriptive qualitative methods. Based on the result of the research, it showed that the total average score of students rating self confidence is 40,95 (high degree of confidence) with the high statement is (students have to take a part in an English Day activities). The data from interview also shows that English day can enhance their ability to communicate directly in English confidently and in the right way in order to motivate them in the process of learning English. And then, it clearly seen that there is the improvement of students' self confidence in speaking English. Besides, the researchers also found that they can add their vocabulary and grammar, increase their pronunciation, they can elaborate their idea based on the theme given, even they can manage their psychology aspects when speak up in front. So, from all research instruments applied, the researchers can conclude that the role English day is really empowering student voice and it also gave big impact for students' self confidence in speaking English.

KEYWORDS: Empowering, Students Voice, English Day Programs, Speaking Self-Confidence.

INTRODUCTION

In English as a Foreign Language (EFL), developing students' speaking skills is still a primary challenge for teachers. The capacity for speaking, which is essential for good communication, remains underdeveloped among many Indonesian students. Wulaningsih et al. (2025). It cannot be deny that speaking plays a big and essential part in mastering one language. To be able to communicate effectively or good communication skills are important and it is not easy work. Students are expected to be able to speak both correctly and clearly including it's pronunciation so that the information conveyed can be understood well by the interlocutor without any misunderstanding of the ideas. But in reality, we found some problems appear, such as lack of student interaction using English in the teaching and learning process, lack of conversation in using English inside or outside the class, even though it is a subject where conversation should be in English. Besides, there are also some factors influence the student in following the teaching learning process, namely: psychological, attitudes, motivation as well as language talent or basic ability of the students which is still minim. Those problems above are their obstacles in increasing their self confidence in speaking English and that will be the researchers' consideration in taking this study.

As we already known that speaking is considered as productive skill, so active classroom participation is an important role in the success of language learning. It means that students who active more in speaking get better in their spoken language, but to make students become a good speaker, it needs more self - confidence in order to build good communication with the other people runing well. self - confidence is an attitude or feeling confident in the ability of oneself so that the person concerned is not too anxious in his/her actions, can feel free to do the things he/she likes and is responsible for the actions, warm and polite in interacting with others, have the impulse to excel and be familiar with the advantages and disadvantages, (Nety & Nurhaeni, 2020: 9). They also adds that to build students' confidence to speak English, the teachers can provide regular opportunities to practice proper pronunciation and intonation, also to converse freely. By doing this, students will experience a greater sense of ability to speak English. Therefore teacher should create a comfortable atmosphere in which learners are encouraged to talk in English and are praised for talking.

Furthermore, Sumanto & Saharani (2023) in their research found that students' confidence appears to be related to their perspective of their speaking ability. They cannot claim to be at ease every time they speak a foreign language because speaking is such a vital element of communication yet they are motivated to learn and practice English. According to the respondents, while confidence is a fantastic place to start in

speaking, it will not take them very far unless they consistently practice enhancing their language competence. The most typical approach is to engage in conversation whenever feasible.

Even though, there are some problems as well as factors influence the student in improving their ability to speak up, but believe that if there is a willingness, so there is also a way to achieve it. And, one of the ways from study program to help the students to practice their speaking skill is through the implementation of English day program. According to Syahfutra Wandu and Siti Niah (2017: 50) that English Day is a program for training and getting used to the usage of English in daily activities where requires the participants to speak English within the agreed time. Students may not employ other languages during the English day. The program can train speakers to have the courage to speak and master the vocabulary. Another function of English day is that it can strengthen the relationship between junior, senior and lecturers, especially lecturers in the English department because the lecturer is the speaker or facilitator in this program.

In addition, Ramadani, L., & Dharmawan, Y. Y. (2025) viewed that in this context, pedagogical interventions such as the English Day program serve as innovative and practical responses to bridge the gap between theoretical learning and functional language use. English Day is designed to immerse students in an English-speaking environment, typically for a full school day, where they are encouraged, if not required, to communicate exclusively in English with teachers and peers. This immersive experience simulates real-life language use and creates opportunities for students to experiment with spoken English in a low-stakes, peer-supported setting.

In the literature on the development of speaking skills among English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners, programs like English Day have been extensively researched as effective strategies for enhancing student self-confidence through interactive and immersive activities. One of the studies is about "Students' Self Confidence in Speaking English" conducted by Nety & Nurhaeni (2020). The result showed that there are some factors founded which causes students' lack self confidence, those are; anxiety, fear of making mistakes, shyness, and lack of vocabulary. Meanwhile, the strategies to overcome students' lack self confidence in speaking English are; Lowering Students' Anxiety in Speaking English, Improving Students' Vocabulary, Boosting Students' Self Confidence, and Forming Group Discussion

Specifically, studies on "empowering student voice", the empowerment of student voices through active participation in language programs remain limited in the context of English Education students. There is no in-depth exploration integrating English Day programs with student voice empowerment in regional universities like UMMU. In Ternate, a region facing accessibility and cultural diversity challenges, English Education students often encounter barriers such as limited opportunities for speaking practice due to resource constraints, which have not been comprehensively examined.

Therefore, this study addresses this gap by investigating the impact of English Day programs on the development of speaking self-confidence among English Education students at UMMU, Ternate. This localized focus is expected to provide practical insights for curriculum and language program development in similar universities, which are underrepresented in the predominantly urban or metropolitan-based international literature. It is hoped that the students' ability and self confidence in speaking English can improve properly so that they are able to express ideas and opinion clearly and in a systematic manner. The problem of this research is Does participation in English Day programs improve EFL students' speaking self-confidence? This study aims to evaluate the impact of the English Day program on the development of speaking self-confidence among English Education students at UMMU, Ternate, with a focus on empowering students' voices through active participation in immersive and interactive activities.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research applied descriptive qualitative method. While, the subject of the study were 20 students and taken randomly from English Department at Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku who had been participated in English day program. The instrument used in the data collection process included observation, questionnaires and interviews. These instruments were used in collecting the data. The data collection started with doing observation, giving the questionnaire to the respondents, then the researchers invited the respondents to have a depth in-person interview as the continuation step in obtaining more detailed data. This questionnaire instrument uses a Liker Scale. The Likert Scale requires the individual's responding of a series of statements by indicating whether he/she is Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) or Strongly Disagree (SD). The students were asked to answer the question by choosing five categories SA=5, A=4, N=3, D=2 and SD=1. The score of questionnaire is based on the table below:

Table 2.1 Likert Scala Rating

Optional	Score
Stongly Agree	5
Agree	4
Neutral	3
Disagree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

Source : jefiza (2011)

Five-point Likert Scale is applied in order to measure the level and type of learning motivation of the subject. The Scale is also used in the questionnaire statement in order to determine the level of agree or disagree with students' answer based on the following criteria.

Table 2.2 Standard of Mean

Mean Range	Interpretation
3,68-5,00	High degree of confidence
2,34-3,67	Moderate degree of motivation
1,00-2,33	Low degree of motivation

Source: jefiza (2011)

RESEARCH RESULT

The study implementation began with an initial observation phase. Then, followed by filling the questionnaire, and last step is a depth in-person interview in order to strengthen the observation and questionnaire data. Thematic analysis of the interview findings showed several key factors that hindered students' speaking performance. These recurring themes shaped the basis for designing the intervention and are summarized in the table below.

1) The Result of Observation

In this study, the researchers did 3 times of observation with different place and different theme. The step in doing observation consist of; opening, main activity and closing, so the result of it can be seen in the following explanation:

In the first meeting, there are some students when they come forward to do presentation, they are still lack self confidence, they could not manage their nervousness and anxiety. Most of them were still afraid to speak up in English because their stock of vocabulary is still minim, and they felt afraid if they make wrong pronunciation. Only some students who had possessed self confidence when they spoke in front. In second and third meeting, even though there are also some students still felt nervous, afraid and lack of grammar as well as vocabulary, but almost of them has got the improvement in speaking English, they have braveness to speak up in front and could manage their nervous, and tried say words based on the right pronunciation.

Based on the result of 3 times of observation, the researchers can conclude that there is the improvement of students' self confidence in speaking English. Besides, the researchers also found that they can add their vocabulary, good enough in pronouncing English words, they can also elaborate their idea based on the theme, even they enjoy very much about this activity and they can manage their psychology aspects when speak up in front.

2) The Result of Questionnaire

Table 3.1 Students' Response on Questionnaire Sheet

No	Statements	Mean	Rating of Self Confidence
1	English Day can enhance my self confidence in speaking English	4,15	High
2	English Day should be continued	4,30	High
3	After joining English Day, I can manage my nervousness, anxiety and fear when speaking in Public.	4,00	High
4	I fell any improvement in my English ability after joining English Day.	3,95	High
5	I am satisfied with English day activities.	3,70	High
6	English Day activities help me learn English orally and directly.	4,3	High
7	Comparing to study English in the classroom, English Day activities are more interesting.	3,75	High
8	All English students have to take a part in an English Day activities.	4,45	High
9	The aim of English Day is to help English students increasing their speaking and basic ptonunciation.	4,15	High
10	I get more motivated in learning English after joining English Day	4,20	High
Total		40,95	High

Table 3.1 above shows about the results of questionnaire related to English students' confidence. The data from the table clearly seen that the total mean for students' confidence is high in rating of confidence level. The total score is 40.95. To find out the total mean score of students' confidence, that is 40.95 the researchers used the formula below:

$$total = \frac{\text{the Amount of Data}}{\text{lots of Data}}, \text{ so the sum of all mean scores in each statement is then divided by the number of data, that is 10 statements.}$$

Statement number 1 with the score of 4.15, statement number 2 with the score of 4.30, statement number 3 with the score of 4.00, statement number 4 with the score of 3.95, statement number 5 with the score of 3.70, statement number 6 with the score of 4.3, statement number 7 with

the score of 3.75, statement number 8 with the score of 4.45, statement number 9 with the score of 4.15, statement number 10 with the score of 4.20.

mean $\frac{\text{total student score}}{\text{total students}}$, thus the total score of all students for statement number 1 is then divided by total number of students namely 20 students. Based on the Likert scale table in the previous section, each student who answered Strongly Agree (SA) got a score = 5, then Agree (A) = 4, Neutral (N) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. For statement number 1, students who answered Strongly Agree were 8 persons, the score were $8 \times 5 = 40$, while those who answered Agree were 9 people, the score was $9 \times 4 = 36$, those who answered neutral was 1 people the score was $1 \times 3 = 3$, while those who answered disagree were 2 people, the score was $2 \times 2 = 4$.

For statement number 2, students who answered strongly agree were 8 people, the score was $8 \times 5 = 40$, while those who answered agree were 10 people, the score $10 \times 4 = 40$, those who answered neutral were 2 people and their score was $2 \times 3 = 6$. The next is for statement number 3, students who answered Strongly Agree were 5 people, the score was $5 \times 5 = 25$, while those answered Agree were 10 people, the score $10 \times 4 = 40$, the last those answered Neutral were 5 people, so the score was $5 \times 3 = 15$.

For statement number 4, students who answered Strongly Agree were 5 people, the score $5 \times 5 = 25$, while those answered Agree were 11 people, the score $11 \times 4 = 44$, then those answered Neutral were 3 people, the score $3 \times 3 = 9$, while those answered Strongly Disagree was 1 people, the score $1 \times 1 = 1$. For the statement 5, students who answered Strongly Agree were 7 people, the score $7 \times 5 = 35$, while those answered Agree were 7 people, the score $7 \times 4 = 28$, then those answered Neutral were 2 people, the score $2 \times 3 = 6$, while those answered Disagree was 1 people, the score $1 \times 2 = 2$, those answered Strongly Disagree were 3 people, the score $3 \times 1 = 3$.

For the statement number 6, student who answered Strongly Agree were 6 people, the score $6 \times 5 = 35$, while those answered Agree were 11 people, the score $11 \times 4 = 44$, while those answered Neutral were 2 people, the score $2 \times 3 = 6$, the next those answered Strongly Disagree was 1 people, the score $1 \times 1 = 1$. For the statement number 7, the student who answered Strongly Agree were 4 people, the score $4 \times 5 = 20$, then those answered Agree were 11, the score $11 \times 4 = 44$, while those answered Neutral were 3 people, the score $3 \times 3 = 9$, those answered Strongly Disagree 2 people, the score $2 \times 1 = 2$.

For the statement number 8, student who answered Strongly Agree were 10 people, the score $10 \times 5 = 50$, those answered Neutral was 1 people, the score $1 \times 3 = 3$. For the statement number 9, student who answer Strongly Agree were 8 people, the score $8 \times 5 = 40$, those answered Agree were 10 people, the score $10 \times 4 = 40$, those answered Neutral were 2 people, the score $2 \times 3 = 6$. For the statement number 10, student who answer Strongly Agree were 8 people, the score $8 \times 5 = 40$, while those answered Agree were 8 people, the score $8 \times 4 = 32$, while those Neutral were 4 people, the score $4 \times 3 = 12$.

To clarify the data above, the researchers presents a chart below for the rating of students' self confident :

Chart of Self Confidence Rating

3) The Result of Interview

Beside observation and questionnaire, the researchers also uses interview as the instrument in order to strengthen the result of observation and questionnaire. So, the summary of the result of interview can be seen in following table:

Table 3.2 Students' Response on Interview's list

No	Questions	Summary of Respondents' Answer
1	What do you think about English day ?	Mostly students gave positive answer about this question. According to them, English day has many benefits, like it could improve their speaking, grammar, and also vocabulary. It could built relationship between senior and junior, and it was very important because they knew how to speak English well.
2	What is your motivation in joining English day ?	There are some reasons for them to join this activity; firstly, it can be able to add their knowledge, they can elaborate their idea and also they have many chances to

		practice. Another answer is that they realize about their speaking ability which is still minim, so hopefully after joining this program they can speak fluently. The last, they wanted to learn about how to pronounce English word correctly, then increase their stock of vocabulary.
3	Do you have obstacles in speaking ?	Everybody said yes. Their respond are various too: the obstacles are: lack of vocabulary, it is still hard to memorize many words, they feel afraid if they produce bad pronunciation or say wrong words, the knowledge of grammar is not adequate yet, also, they do not ready with the theme or topic given by facilitator.
4	Do you think English day could improve your English Ability ? and why ?	All students answer yes. Their reasons are: It can Enhance their potential in learning English. According to them, study in the classroom is not enough because lack of practice, but conversally in English day, it full of practice and more challenges, so it can added knowledge, vocabulary and friends, in addition it can reduce the feeling of nervous, and finally their speaking English become excellent.
5	What interesting programs do you like in English day ?	Some respondents like game because it is so interesting, and the other like conversation with friends because they known each other and also describing something.
6	What kinds of learning method do you like in English day ?	They like public speaking because this method can train their mental to speak and explore the idea, and it is very affected to improve their talent and another answer is game.
7	What are the disadvantage and advantages that you feel after joining English day?	For them, there is not disadvantage. This program is really possess a lot of advantages, namely they are more brave to come forward to speak up, it build their self confidence, more practice make them perfect, or reduce their wrong pronunciation, they have a lot of vocabulary, also, possess many friends.
8	Is there any difference between learning English in classroom and learning English in English day ?	Yes, very different, it has big potential. In class full of theory and lack of practice, but in English day we learn about how we trained mental, skill, knowledge and more practice. In class, they are not nervous, but outside of the class everybody should speak English, so it makes them fell nervous. In class is more formal for example: when a lecturer gave a question, and the students must answer the question based on topic, but in English day they are free to give their opinion, so the point is it can improve speaking skill.
9	Does English day help English Students improving their English Skill ? and why ?	Yes, it does. Because many students who enter in English Department at Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku have a little bit basic of English, thus by following English day, they can learn to enhance their speaking skill, learn about English alphabet, grammar, vocabulary, and another knowledge.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data presented before, whether it is from the result of observation, questionnaire as well as interview, it obviously showed that the role of English day program gave a big impact for the students of English department at Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku, Indonesia. It is not only increase students' self confidence, but more than that it can increase their ability in mastering English, such as it can add their knowledge of grammar, add their vocabulary, their pronunciation is good enough, they have the braveness to speak in public, and the performance in speaking English is more better, even van add their friends. Thus, this program actually can empower students voice, meaning that they try to speak up in English eventhough there are many obstacles, but the result is their speaking self-confidence more alive and this is accordance with the opinion from Herpratiwi and Purnomo (2015:3) that English Club is an activity extracurricular which aims to develop students' abilities in the field of English.

Besides, the situation or environment created for full of speaking English became the challenges for students to accustomed to speak full English, and it actually makes them "perforce" to use English in every activity they run in the program. According to Robert I. Rhodes (2005:64) that English day is a program model differs from the aforementioned bilingual models in that students receive instruction in English only. This program also as a system of training which can give knowledge about English components.

Based on explanation before, it is clear that in English day, students learn many things and it clearly gives many changes for exploring themselves too. So, the researchers can concluded that English Students of Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku can improve their self confidence in speaking skill. This is also the same with the research done by Nety & hurhaeni with the title: " Students' Self Confidence in Speaking English" founded that there are some factors founded which causes students' lack self of confidence, those are anxiety, fear of making mistake, shyness, and lack of vocabulary. (2020: 16). But, after joining English day program, they can overcome those factors and obstacle, so this is very good for students and lectures in the teaching and learning process because they can practice their English abilities and have a trigger to be more active and be confident in expressing their idea using English. As mentioned by Fuentesal-Garcia J et al (2025) that in this sense, fostering student confidence will be a key aspect that teachers can develop in teaching-learning contexts.

Moreover, the above results are strengthened by the research from Ramadani, L., & Dharmawan, Y. Y. (2025) confirm that English Day program significantly improved students' speaking proficiency, it also presented sociolinguistic challenges such as anxiety and self-consciousness. Nonetheless, consistent exposure to English and supportive social environments helped foster students' confidence and communicative skills. As

said by Aditama et al (2025) that engaged students often display increased motivation, active participation, and a sustained interest in learning, which altogether contribute to improved academic performance and long-term.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings and discussion, it can be concluded that the role of English day program gave a big impact for the students of English department at Muhammadiyah University of North Maluku. This program is very important and should be run continuously because it can empower student voice and develop the speaking self-confidence, and even it can motivate them more active in the process of learning English. Besides, they can add their vocabulary, grammar, their pronunciation is good enough, they can elaborate their idea based on the theme, they enjoy very much about this activity and they can manage their psychological aspects when they speak up. So, it can be said that English Day program can give the positive contribution for the increasing of students' speaking competence and their speaking self-confidence.

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